

THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: Currently, we can find artificial intelligence in many areas of society. The influence of artificial intelligence is growing day by day. The use of artificial intelligence is growing, including in education. Artificial intelligence is a branch of science created by the processes of human intelligence with the help of machines, especially computer systems. The main goal of AI is to smooth out the interactions between humans and machines as it is accessed by intelligent system, human language processing, speech recognition and machine vision. The demand for AI is growing around the world. Be it real estate or digital marketing, artificial intelligence has revolutionized every sector and the education sector is no exception. In fact, it plays a huge role when it comes to teaching and learning. Schools and colleges are now using artificial intelligence to improve teaching methods and achieve better results. In this article, we will explain the influence and importance of artificial intelligence in education system of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, AI, Internet, education, machine learning, educational data mining, algorithm.

Before the introduction of computers and other related technologies, teachers and students engaged in instruction and learning mechanically or through the pure application of natural human effort. With the advent of microcomputers and, by extension, personal computers in the 1970s, they provided greater computing power and marked an important transition to electronic computing for the mass market. It is generally agreed that the development of electronic computing machines in particular, and their availability to various organizations in various sectors of the

economy, was accelerated by the development of personal computers in the 1970s [1]. The development of personal computers has allowed individuals and other non-governmental organizations to own computers and use them for a variety of reasons. These transitions herald the proliferation of computers in various sectors of the economy and society.

Computer and information and communication technologies have continued to evolve over the years, leading to the development of artificial intelligence. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the ability of machines to adapt to new situations, cope with emerging situations, solve problems, answer questions, make device plans, and perform various other functions that require a certain level of intelligence usually found in humans. Another definition defines artificial intelligence as the study of the intelligent behavior of humans, animals and machines and the attempt to translate such behavior into an artifact such as computers and related technologies. Based on these definitions, it is clear that artificial intelligence is the culmination of computers, computer-related technologies, machines and innovations in information and communication technology and developments that enable computers to perform human-like or human-like functions.

It is noted that new forms of technology will fill our lives and captivate our youth, in which case schools may have no choice but to make room for them. Therefore, the focus of this study is how stakeholders from the fields of law, business, education and engineering perceive this development and how they envision artificial intelligence in relation to education. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to explore what the use of artificial intelligence in education means and what implications it may have for the future of education, according to the views of participants from different sectors.

We need many techniques and technologies to apply artificial intelligence in education. Such as programming (web development, mobile development, etc.), machine learning algorithms (regression, classification, clustering) and the Internet.

As mentioned above, we will look at this in detail. Currently, we cannot imagine many areas without programming. Programming helps implement applications created using artificial intelligence.

The next method we'll look at is machine learning algorithms.

In educational technology, automation plays a vital role. This helps teachers identify student success factors and weaknesses. They employ information-centered personalized learning strategies, adaptive curricula, predictive modeling using machine learning and artificial intelligence, and monitor the quality of teaching within their curriculum. Analyzing teachers' data helps them understand the strengths and weaknesses of their students' learning because it promotes a deeply ingrained cultural process that relies on accurate information as input to produce optimal outcomes (outcomes for students). Artificial education, data science, and alumni are all incorporated into the machine learning system to improve online learning. Artificial intelligence will one day make it possible to customize educational software for each student. Student-friendly adaptive learning software and games are already available in the market. One of the most important uses of artificial intelligence in education is to make learning more seamless and remove personal information from the equation.

We need one more method, this is the Internet. The above processes require high Internet speed. High-speed Internet helps [4] take full advantage of applications created on the basis of artificial intelligence. results

Artificial intelligence and machine learning are key drivers of growth and innovation in any industry, and it is no exception in the education sector. Artificial intelligence has advanced significantly across a wide range of industries since the advent of robots and voice-controlled machines. Artificial intelligence has truly enhanced the work of those who have toiled for hours. This allows educators to focus on developing engaging and challenging curriculum while automating much of the internal support work for them.

With the right courses, better teacher-student communication, and more time for other activities, artificial intelligence can have a significant impact on students' educational journeys. In the following section, several advantages are delineated.

Personalization

One of the hottest topics in education right now is the idea of tailoring learning to the unique needs of each student. Through the use of artificial intelligence, students can now learn based on their own unique experiences and preferences. Artificial intelligence can adapt to the specific needs of each student, taking into account their current level of knowledge, learning speed and desired learning outcomes. AI-powered solutions can also analyze students' previous learning histories to identify areas of weakness and recommend courses best suited for improvement, providing multiple opportunities for personalized learning.

Training

Due to their busy schedules, many teachers are unable to accommodate students who need extra help after school - homeschooling or on weekends. In these cases, AI tutors and chatbots are ideal solutions.

Operative response

When an inquiry is posed and a response is received after a lapse of three days, it engenders a sense of frustration. On a daily basis, educators and academic staff are inundated with recurring inquiries. The expeditious resolution of student queries can be achieved within seconds through the utilization of support automation and conversational intelligence facilitated by artificial intelligence. This not only accrues significant time savings for instructors but also enhances the accessibility of information for students in their quest for answers.

Comprehensive assistance

Students have the opportunity to engage in learning at their convenience and from any location, courtesy of artificial intelligence-based tools. Continuous 24/7 accessibility facilitates students in seeking educational resources that best suit their needs, eliminating the necessity of awaiting teacher approvals. Consequently,

students from around the world can access high-quality education without incurring travel or accommodation expenses.

By automating tasks, analyzing student performance, and reducing educational gaps, artificial intelligence has the potential to liberate teachers' time and assist them in more effectively serving their students.

Task automation

Using the computing power of artificial intelligence, routine tasks such as grading jobs and testing learning models can be automated. According to a Telegraph survey, teachers spend 40% of their time planning lessons, grading tests and completing administrative work.

Usage of AI Among Students:

The study surveyed students from high schools, lyceums/colleges, and universities to gauge the extent of AI usage. Figure 1 depicts the percentage of students using AI for educational purposes, personal use, and those who do not use AI, whereas 2 figure represents in what field of education AI is used.

Figure 1 shows that the majority of students prefer using AI for educational purposes. Among university students, 64% use AI for educational purposes, while 18% use it for personal use, and 18% do not use AI. For high school students, 78.5% use AI for educational purposes, 14.2% for personal use, and 7.1% do not use AI. Among lyceum/college students, 72.7% use AI for educational purposes, 25% for personal use, and 2.2% do not use AI.

Figure 2 demonstrates that a significant percentage of students utilize AI for writing essays, including idea generation and grammar correction. Additionally, a considerable portion of students use AI for solving math, physics, and chemistry problems.

Request responses

AI-powered chatbots can answer a wide range of common and repetitive questions commonly asked by students without involving a teacher because they have access to the school's entire knowledge base. Artificial intelligence frees up time for educators to work on other aspects of their jobs, such as lesson planning, curriculum development, and student engagement.

Future of artificial intelligence in the education system

When it comes to smartphones and other home appliances, voice to text has become a common feature. But what if we went further than just setting timers and ordering food? Using machine learning, speech-to-text solutions can be used. Technologies such as natural language processing (NLP) and automatic voice recognition (AVR) can have a significant impact on the way students learn and conduct their research. AVR technology can automatically generate transcripts of any audio or video by converting the spoken word into text. Summarizing, highlighting topics, and tracking student participation are all possible ways to use NLP in the classroom. Thanks to technology in education, you can access a wide range of information. Higher education teaches students to specialize and narrow their interests. Artificial intelligence can make use of more information when [6] machine learning is used to augment lectures.

The use of artificial intelligence (platform) in the following cases can be effective:

1. In the education system of the poorest countries
2. Teacher shortage
3. Pandemic period

We will look at each case mentioned above in detail.

The first case: due to economic problems, many countries in the world cannot spend enough money on education. Educational buildings, educational materials, teaching tools, and teacher salaries require large expenditures. The platform can help solve problems where less money is being spent on education.

In the second case, there may be a shortage of teachers in all regions of the country. This case is not related to money, as in the first case. In this case, the shortage of teachers can be replaced by the platform.

Third case: Due to the coronavirus, which emerged in Wuhan in 2019 and spread throughout the world to the point of a pandemic, students in many countries around

the world were unable to attend school. As a result, the quality of education in schools has declined. Using the platform is effective in every case mentioned above.

Conclusion. In this article, we have examined the role of artificial intelligence within the educational system of Uzbekistan. The following observations can be drawn regarding this process: the cost-effectiveness, the potential for reusable educational materials, students' ability to engage with subjects on a convenient platform at their own pace and time, the allowance for students to revisit subjects on the platform, the provision of personalized approaches to each student, and the evaluation of student examinations at the end of modules or courses through artificial intelligence-based systems.

However, it is crucial to underscore that further research is imperative to acquire a more precise comprehension of the benefits and constraints associated with AI's influence on the educational landscape. As AI technology evolves, it becomes paramount to explore its potential ramifications on the learning process, student engagement, and the overall educational experience. By addressing ethical considerations, ensuring data security, and fostering transparency, AI can be seamlessly integrated into the educational framework, thereby augmenting pedagogical practices and alleviating the burdens on educators. Subsequent research endeavors should aim to delve deeper into these realms to maximize the advantageous applications of AI in the realm of education within Uzbekistan.

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